

GREENDT

D7.3. PROJECT WEBSITE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the development and launch of the official GREENDT website. It describes the overall structure of the site, including its main pages and sections. As an integral element of the GREENDT Project's Dissemination and Communication Plan, the website serves as a key platform for all related communication activities and the dissemination of project results. Its design, management, and ongoing maintenance are therefore considered core operational tasks. The website is intended to function as a dynamic, evolving platform that will adapt and expand in alignment with the project's progress.

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1 Introduction

The GREENDT website has been structured and designed as the main platform for disseminating the project's work, targeting both the general public and experts in the field. It serves as a central hub for stakeholders, media, and anyone interested in the project. Online and offline dissemination & communication strategies or campaigns will be complementary, with the shared goal of driving traffic to the website.

The website provides detailed information about key aspects of the GREENDT project at a local, national and international level, serving as a key tool for public dissemination. It is intended to be regularly updated with content such as upcoming meetings, events participation, training sessions, dissemination activities, conferences, scientific publications, newsletters, news, photo galleries, and many more. The platform will play a central role in facilitating communication among project partners, government agencies, industries, academic institutions, NGOs, civil society and the broader public, ensuring the wide visibility of project outcomes.

It is open to the public and accessible to anyone with an internet connection. The following domain name was registered to host the website: <https://greendt-project.eu/>

As the work package leader, FEUGA was the partner in charge of the website construction, and it will be responsible for its maintenance, being accessible to all interested parties during and at least 2 years after the end of the project's lifetime. The website was designed aiming to follow one of the work package's main objectives, which is: developing a strategy for communicating project results to target groups such as universities, government bodies, and industries, facilitating participation and dialogue.

Furthermore, FEUGA has developed a dedicated Staff Intranet using Microsoft SharePoint, integrated within Microsoft Teams, to enhance internal communication and collaboration among project partners. This cloud-based workspace offers a range of features, including group mailing, a centralized file repository, and other collaborative tools designed to support efficient project coordination.

Responsive Web Design ensures that the GREENDT website displays optimally across all devices, including desktops, tablets, and smartphones.

2 The GREENDT website structure

The website has been developed using WordPress, allowing the project management team to easily update the content throughout the duration of the project. All sections feature the GREENDT logo at the top and include a reference to the European Union funding programme at the bottom of the page.

Figure 1 GREENDT website footer

At the top, next to the logo, there are six navigation labels, two of them with a drop-down menu, providing access to the various sections available. The footer also contains links to the GREENDT's social media channels.

Figure 2 Main sections of the GREENDT website

These six navigation labels constitute the main sections of the website and are as follows:

- Home
- About (divided into three sub-sections)
- Consortium
- Resources (divided into five sub-sections)
- News
- Contact

2.1 Home

The main page presents the GREENDT project at a glance, explaining the mission and main objectives of the project. As we scroll down, we can note the members of the consortium grouped together, along with a display of the most recent news, right at the bottom of the page, so the visitors can immediately be informed about the latest actions within the project.

Figure 3 Home page

2.2 About

This section brings together all relevant information regarding the project origin, main goals, challenges, contribution and expected outcomes.

This page is split into the following sub-sections:

- Project
- Objectives
- Work Packages

2.2.1 Project

The first subsection provides a concise overview of the project’s background, its scope and objectives, the key challenges it addresses, and the contributions it aims to make in response to those challenges.

Figure 4 Project section

2.2.2 Objectives

The project’s objectives are illustrated in three interactive information containers. The first side of the container shows the title of each objective, which is expanded on a second slide when hovering the cursor over it. This serves as a small interactive element to help sort and summarize information.

Figure 5 Objectives section

2.2.3 Work Packages

This section presents the Work Packages through seven dedicated information modules—one for each WP. Each module includes the WP number, title, duration, lead beneficiary, and a brief description highlighting the key objectives and main activities. Consistent with the overall design of the GREENDT website, these modules incorporate the project’s corporate color scheme. The purpose of this section is to provide a clear and accessible summary of the tasks associated with each Work Package.

Work Packages

Work Package 1: Project Management

■ Duration: M1 – M36
● Lead Beneficiary: Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo (Portugal)

Work Package 1 focuses on ensuring the effective, efficient, and sustainable management of the GreenDT project by applying professional project management standards. The work package guarantees quality, timeliness, and financial compliance while fostering collaboration among partners.

Key Objectives:

- ✔ **Effective Consortium Coordination:** Ensuring smooth decision-making and communication across the consortium.
- ✔ **Risk Identification and Mitigation:** Proactively identifying and addressing potential risks throughout the project.
- ✔ **Compliance with Grant Agreement:** Ensuring financial regulations and agreement terms are strictly followed.
- ✔ **Quality Assurance and Reporting:** Monitoring the project’s progress and providing regular reports to guarantee quality.

Main Activities:

- ✔ **Project Communication:** Regular in-person, virtual, and Steering Committee meetings.
- ✔ **Quality Assurance:** Utilizing GANTT charts, risk management strategies, and checkpoint reports to monitor progress.
- ✔ **Financial Management:** Overseeing budgets, ensuring timely partner payments, and conducting internal evaluations.
- ✔ **Sustainability:** Developing strategies for environmental and social sustainability throughout the project.

Work Package 2: Research on Environmental Priorities & Higher Education Strategy in Uzbekistan

■ Duration: M1 – M12
● Lead Beneficiary: Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute (Uzbekistan)

Work Package 2 focuses on analyzing European Union environmental policies and adapting best practices to the context of Uzbekistan, aiming to enhance environmental education and industry practices.

Key Objectives:

- ✔ **Assess European Union Environmental Policies:** Examine European Union environmental policies and the European Green Deal strategy.
- ✔ **Identify Uzbekistan’s Environmental Challenges:** Conduct surveys and a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis to determine key environmental issues.
- ✔ **Develop Recommendations for Improving Environmental Culture:** Provide actionable recommendations for Higher Education Institutions and Industries in Uzbekistan.
- ✔ **Create a Strategic Plan for Environmental Education:** Formulate a strategy to introduce environmental science courses in Higher Education Institutions.

Main Activities:

- ✔ **Policy Analysis:** Adapt European Union environmental policies to fit the specific needs of Uzbekistan.
- ✔ **Surveys & SWOT Analysis:** Identify and analyze environmental challenges faced by Uzbekistan’s industries and Higher Education Institutions.
- ✔ **Measure Development:** Develop solutions based on successful European Union practices to address Uzbekistan’s environmental challenges.
- ✔ **Strategic Planning:** Create legal and educational recommendations for enhancing environmental education.

Work Package 3: Training of Trainers-Based Pedagogical Framework for a Master’s in Environmental Engineering

■ Duration: M1 – M12
● Lead Beneficiary: Universidad de Vigo (Spain)

Work Package 3 focuses on establishing a robust pedagogical framework and Training of Trainers program to support a new Master’s in Environmental Engineering across universities in Uzbekistan.

Key Objectives:

- ✔ **Environmental Engineering Handbook Development:** Create a comprehensive guide aligned with learning objectives and adaptable to Uzbek universities.
- ✔ **Didactic Material Creation:** Develop educational resources on sustainable energy, natural radiation, and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), tailored to regional needs.
- ✔ **Training of Trainers Sessions:** Organize training sessions in the European Union (Month 6) and Uzbekistan (Month 10) to build faculty expertise and ensure knowledge dissemination.

Main Activities:

- ✔ **Handbook Development:** Conduct a needs assessment and develop a curriculum framework and structured program.
- ✔ **Educational Toolkit:** Compile lectures, case studies, multimedia resources, and regionally adapted teaching materials.
- ✔ **Training of Trainers Implementation:** Organize practical sessions focused on engineering diplomacy, equity, sustainability, and pollution, both in Europe and Uzbekistan.

Work Package 4: Deployment of Environmental Engineering Nexus

■ Duration: M7 – M30
● Lead Beneficiary: Fundación Empresa Universidad Gallega (Spain)

Work Package 4 focuses on building a strong link between academia and industry in Environmental Engineering through the establishment of laboratories, industry-university collaborations, and a digital platform for knowledge sharing and professional networking.

Key Objectives:

- ✔ **Environmental Engineering Laboratory Standards:** Research and implement European Union-referenced Environmental Engineering laboratory standards to support both academia and industry.
- ✔ **Industry-University Collaboration:** Form partnerships for Environmental Engineering services, student internships, and knowledge sharing.
- ✔ **E-Society Development:** Create a digital platform integrating sectors like Energy, Industry, Transportation, Education, and Civil Society to address environmental challenges.

Main Activities:

- ✔ **Environmental Engineering Laboratory Implementation:** Develop laboratory infrastructure based on European Union standards.
- ✔ **Industry-Academic Network:** Formalize collaborations through Memorandums of Understanding, facilitate internships, and enhance Environmental Engineering-linked services.
- ✔ **E-Society Deployment:** Launch a platform for professionals, researchers, and students to exchange knowledge and innovations in Environmental Engineering.

We value your privacy

Figure 6 Work packages section (1/2)

Work Package 5: Dedicated Capacity Building on European Environmental Policy and Environmental Engineering

Duration: M13 – M36
Lead Beneficiary: Tashkent Kimyo International University (Uzbekistan)

Work Package 5 focuses on building capacity in Environmental Engineering and enhancing knowledge of European environmental policies among stakeholders in Uzbekistan and Central Asia. This work package lays the foundation for improving the quality of education and research in Environmental Engineering, focusing on European Union best practices, regulations, and sustainable development.

Key Objectives:

- Train Higher Education Institution Staff in Environmental Engineering:** Offer training on environmental engineering topics to enhance sustainability practices in Uzbekistan's Higher Education Institutions.
- European Union Policy Webinars:** Organize webinars on the European Green Deal, climate change, energy, and environmental protection.
- Develop an Online Platform:** Create a digital platform offering Open Courseware and Open Educational Resources for Environmental Engineering courses.
- Address Digital Skills Gap:** Promote the use of digital tools to bridge the skills gap in education, industry, and research.
- Mobility Agreements:** Facilitate student exchanges between academic institutions to enhance international collaboration.

Main Activities:

- Deployment of Environmental Engineering Training for Higher Education Institution Staff:** Implement specialized training for staff at Universidade de Aveiro, integrating European Union best practices.
- Webinars on European Union Environmental Policies:** Deliver webinars on the European Green Deal, energy, and environmental standards, focusing on sustainability and international cooperation.
- Development of an E-learning Platform:** Launch a digital platform offering free Environmental Engineering courses and support for Master's students.
- Establishment of Mobility Agreements:** Create mobility frameworks for student exchanges, promoting long-term international collaboration.

Work Package 6: Development of Environmental Engineering Master Degrees

Duration: M7 – M36
Lead Beneficiary: Andijan State Technical Institute (Uzbekistan)

Work Package 6 focuses on developing a new Master's degree program in Environmental Engineering that meets national and international educational standards. This work package aims to align the curriculum with labor market needs, enhance industry relevance, and incorporate best practices from European Union partner universities.

Key Objectives:

- Assess European Union Environmental Policies:** Examine European Union environmental policies and the European Green Deal strategy.
- Development of Study Plans and Teaching Materials:** Create a detailed study plan, syllabi, and innovative teaching materials for the new Master's program in Environmental Engineering.
- Accreditation and Implementation:** Ensure the new Master's program is accredited and successfully implemented to meet academic and professional standards.

Main Activities:

- Research and Compilation on European Union Master's Study Plans:** Conduct research visits to European Union partner Higher Education Institutions and analyze curricula to inform curriculum development in Uzbekistan.
- Development of New Environmental Engineering Master's Curriculum:** Develop a new study plan, course syllabi, and innovative teaching materials based on European Union practices and national priorities.
- Accreditation and Implementations:** Submit the new curriculum and materials for approval and accreditation by national authorities to ensure successful implementation.

Work Package 7: Exploitation, Dissemination, and Communication

Duration: M1 – M36
Lead Beneficiary: Fundación Empresa Universidad Gallega (Spain)

Work Package 7 focuses on the broad dissemination, communication, and long-term exploitation of the GreenDT project's results. This work package aims to maximize the visibility of the project, engage key stakeholders, and ensure the sustainability and replicability of the project outcomes.

Key Objectives:

- Dissemination and Promotion:** Spread the project outcomes to identified target groups and promote their long-term use.
- Multi-layer Communication Strategy:** Engage a variety of audiences, including stakeholders and policymakers, through a comprehensive communication approach.
- Exploitation of Results:** Ensure the long-term accessibility and relevance of project outcomes through sustainable strategies.

Main Activities:

- Communication and Dissemination Planning:** Develop a strategy for communicating project results to target groups such as universities, government bodies, and industries.
- Development of Dissemination Materials:** Create newsletters, leaflets, roll-ups, videos, and organize dissemination events such as conferences to raise awareness of project results.
- Communication Platforms:** Create and maintain the project website, social media accounts, and engage in digital campaigns to increase project visibility.
- Dissemination Conferences:** Organize conferences to share project results and engage stakeholders in discussions on future perspectives in environmental engineering and higher education.
- Sustainability and Exploitation Planning:** Develop strategies for the long-term sustainability and exploitation of project results, ensuring the continued use and impact of the platforms created during the project.

Figure 7 Work packages section (2/2)

2.3 Consortium

The “Consortium” page features a list of all GREENDT partners, alphabetically sorted, including their logo, country of origin and a hyperlink to each institution's official website. They all appear inside a container module, which is styled with the colors of the project.

Consortium

The **GreenDT** project brings together a diverse consortium of leading institutions from Uzbekistan, Portugal, and Spain, united by a common goal to advance environmental education. This collaboration brings together leading academic institutions and government agencies, each leveraging their expertise to promote sustainable development and advance environmental engineering education.

■ Portugal | ■ Uzbekistan | ■ Spain

Andijan State Technical Institute

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Central Asian University of Environmental and Climate Change Studies Green University

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Fundación Empresa Universidad Gallega

■ Spain

Visit website

Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo (Coordinator)

■ Portugal

Visit website

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Tashkent Kimyo International University

■ Uzbekistan

Visit website

Universidade de Aveiro

■ Portugal

Visit website

Universidad de Vigo

■ Spain

Visit website

Figure 8 Consortium page

2.4 Resources

This section includes a significant portion of the project's dissemination activities at different levels.

The page is split in the following sub-sections:

- Deliverables
- Materials
- Videos
- Gallery
- Newsletter

2.4.1 Deliverables

This section features a list of all public deliverables produced by the GREENDT project. Each deliverable will be made available for download in PDF format once it has been reviewed and officially accepted by the European Commission.

Deliverables of the project are documents describing the research process, results, and conclusions, prepared at distinct stages of the project.

The following public deliverables are foreseen in the project:

Deliverable D2.1 – Survey and SWOT analysis Report	Not available yet
Deliverable D2.2 – EE Strategic Plan Report in Higher Education	Not available yet
Deliverable D3.1 – EE Handbook	Not available yet
Deliverable D3.2 – Toolkit of didactic materials	Not available yet
Deliverable D5.3 – EE e-learning Platform	Not available yet
Deliverable D6.1 – EE Master study plans Report	Not available yet
Deliverable D6.3 – Accreditation and implementation documents	Not available yet
Deliverable D7.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan	Not available yet
Deliverable D7.2 – Sustainability and Exploitation Plan	Not available yet
Deliverable D7.3 – Project Website	Not available yet
Deliverable D7.4 – Dissemination Activities Intermediate Report	Not available yet
Deliverable D7.5 – Dissemination Activities Final Report	Not available yet

Figure 9 Deliverable section

2.4.2 Materials

This section of the website hosts all materials related to the project's visual identity, provided in easily accessible and quick-to-download formats. It currently includes the GREENDT logo and will be expanded to feature additional items such as a leaflet and a roll-up banner. There is also the possibility of including posters or other publicity materials the project deems relevant to produce.

Materials

GREENDT will develop materials that showcase its objectives, events, activities, and progress. Stay updated and explore the resources released throughout the project's duration – available for reading and download!

Logo

Download

Figure 10 Materials section

2.4.3 Videos

This section will showcase videos related to the project, including original content produced by the GREENDT team, as well as external videos in which the project is featured or mentioned.

Videos

Discover **GREENDT** in action! This section features videos highlighting the project's key goals, developments, events, and achievements. Watch expert insights, event highlights, and project milestones as we work to modernize higher education, develop a skilled workforce, and address critical environmental challenges like climate change, water scarcity, and pollution.

Stay tuned for updates and new content!

Figure 11 Videos section

2.4.4 Gallery

This section offers a visual journey through the project's progress by displaying several image galleries. These galleries include photos from events in which the project has participated—both internally organized and external engagements—capturing key moments and milestones.

Welcome to the **GREENDT** gallery, where we capture the essence of our mission to modernize Environmental Engineering education in Uzbekistan.

This space will showcase key milestones, achievements, and behind-the-scenes moments, offering a visual journey through the project's progress. Each image reflects the dedication, collaboration, and innovation driving our project forward.

Explore, get inspired, and witness the impact of our work as we build a more sustainable future!

**Kick-Off Meeting (17-18 February, 2025
in Tashkent, Uzbekistan)**

Figure 12 Gallery section

2.4.5 Newsletter

The newsletter is another major part of the project's dissemination tasks. An annual newsletter will be distributed between relevant target groups, stakeholders and the general public, providing every subscriber with all information about the project's outcomes, future plans and activities.

The page contains a subscription form generated using Mailchimp. Once published, the newsletter will also be available for download in this section, recompiling all generated throughout the project's duration.

Stay updated on **GREENDT's** latest advancements in modernizing Environmental Engineering education in Uzbekistan!

Subscribe to our annual newsletter to receive key updates on our progress, events, and innovations. Once published, newsletters will also be available here.

[Subscribe here!](#)

Figure 13 Newsletter section

2.5 News

The “News” page is designed to provide the latest updates on the Project’s activities, offering a quick overview of recent developments. The articles are sorted by date of release, and include a preview with a front cover image, a title, the date, a few lines from the text, and a Read More interactive option.

This page will be constantly updated with the latest material such as upcoming meetings, participation in events, dissemination actions, conferences, etc.

To keep the website attractive for external users, all partners are requested to report to FEUGA any potential news related to the project that could be added to this section.

The website will compile more than 35 news articles accumulated during the project’s lifetime, and 15 additional entries during 2 years after the end of the project.

Figure 14 News page

2.6 Contact

The GREENDT website includes a contact form that requires users to provide their name, email address, and a message. Once submitted, the message is sent to the central project email address (info@greendt-project.eu), which is monitored by FEUGA’s communication team. They are responsible for reviewing incoming messages and forwarding them to the appropriate project partner. The form also includes a mandatory checkbox for users to accept the Data Protection Policy, ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations.

In addition, three contact icons have been added to link directly to the project’s social media profiles on Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube, providing users with quick access to GREENDT’s online presence and updates.

Contact

Have questions or want to collaborate? We'd love to hear from you!

Whether you're a student, researcher, industry expert, or institution interested in the GREENDT project, feel free to reach out.

In the meantime, you can stay informed about the GREENDT project's progress by **subscribing to our newsletter** or following our **social media accounts** for the latest updates, insights, and opportunities to engage!

Name *

Email *

Comment or Message *

I agree with the Data Protection Policy.*

Submit

Figure 15 Contact page

3 Measuring results

Website performance will be monitored and evaluated using integrated analytics provided by Metricool. In addition to analyzing social media engagement, this tool offers comprehensive website metrics, including personalized visualizations and graphs on visitor demographics, geographic location, traffic sources, most visited sections, and detailed post statistics.

As previously noted, the website will feature over 35 news articles published throughout the project's duration, with an additional 15 entries planned for the two years following its completion. Dissemination efforts will also be supported through the communication channels of partner universities, including their websites and social media platforms.

Key performance indicators (KPIs) related to website traffic and user engagement will be tracked regularly and shared with consortium partners to ensure continued alignment with the project's communication and dissemination goals.

4 Maintenance

The GREENDT website is maintained **continuously throughout the project duration (M1–M36)** and will remain **online for at least two additional years** after the project's conclusion to ensure sustainability and long-term access to project outcomes.

Maintenance activities are overseen by the designated communication lead partner and include:

- **Content updates:** Regular publication of news items, with a target of **≥35 articles during the project** and **≥15 articles post-project**
- **Technical upkeep:** Ensuring server availability, performance optimization, security updates, and full accessibility compliance
- **Analytics monitoring:** Performance and traffic data are tracked using **Metricool**, which provides insights into user engagement and reach
- **Backup and archiving:** Regular backups and content archiving are performed to preserve data integrity
- **Link and media verification:** Periodic checks to ensure all downloadable resources and embedded content are functioning properly

Each project partner contributes to the content pipeline by sharing materials, event summaries, and results, coordinated through the shared dissemination Excel file and editorial planning managed by the communication team.

This ongoing maintenance ensures that the GREENDT website remains a **dynamic, reliable, and visible resource** for stakeholders and the public well beyond the project's formal end.

5 Conclusion

The GREENDT website has been designed as a comprehensive and dynamic platform to support the project's dissemination and communication efforts. By providing a central hub for information, updates, and resources, the website plays a pivotal role in engaging stakeholders, disseminating project results, and facilitating communication among partners and the broader public. With its user-friendly structure, responsive design, and regular content updates, the website ensures that the project's progress and outcomes are effectively shared at local, national, and international levels.

Furthermore, the integration of analytics tools like Metricool allows for continuous monitoring of the website's performance, ensuring that key metrics are tracked and used to refine ongoing dissemination strategies. As the project moves forward, the website will continue to evolve, maintaining its relevance and accessibility to stakeholders and supporting the long-term visibility of the GREENDT project's impact.

The website, together with additional promotional and dissemination materials, will remain accessible for at least two years after the project's completion, further solidifying its role as a key resource for information and engagement.